

LINGUISTIC CREATIVITY IN FANTASY LITERATURE: A STUDY OF NEW WORD FORMATION IN THE HARRY POTTER BOOKS

Akhmadullina Raykhona

The second-year Master's student, KFU, Linguistics, Russia, Kazan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13982506>

Annotation: This article examines the neologisms' structural and semantic characteristics in J.K. Rowling's Harry Potter book series, highlighting the inventive language that enhances the magical setting. The examination of the morphological and semantic characteristics that contribute to the effectiveness and memorability of new words, such as spell names, character names, and creature species, is part of the analytic process. In addition to word construction processes like addition, affixation, and mixing, the article also explores the cultural and symbolic connotations connected to mythology, folklore, and linguistic traditions. The findings demonstrate how neologisms clarify character differences, contribute to the fantastical atmosphere, and increase the reader's sense of absorption in the magical realm.

Key words: English, literature, Harry Potter, semantics, neologisms, British, meaning, new words.

The Harry Potter book series by J.K. Rowling is one of the most successful and influential literary works of our time. With over 500 million copies sold worldwide, the books have captured the hearts of readers of all ages and cultures. One of the most interesting aspects of the Harry Potter series is the language used by the author, which is rich in new and creative words. These words are not only important for understanding the world of Harry Potter, but also for understanding the process of word formation and the linguistic creativity of authors. This thesis will explore the structural and semantic features of new words in the Harry Potter series, analyzing how they are formed, what they mean, and how they contribute to the richness and complexity of the series richness and complexity of the series.

Theoretical aspects of neologisms in literature. The neologism is widely used in literature in order to make the plot of the various literature works more fulfilling and engaging. In the case of the fantasy genre, new words are not only a means of characterizing the characters and their surroundings, but also serve to create a believable world where magic and magical creatures are perceived by the reader as an integral part of reality.

The Harry Potter series has been widely celebrated for its linguistic creativity, particularly its use of new and inventive words. As literary scholar Nickianne Moody notes, "Rowling's language is one of the most remarkable

things about the books...her inventiveness and her humour combine to make the Harry Potter books a linguistic delight". The use of neologisms in the series has been credited with creating a unique and immersive world, as well as reflecting the language practices and concerns of contemporary culture. As language scholar Michael Adams argues, "Rowling's creation of words in the Harry Potter series is remarkable...the books' language reveals a deep and often whimsical playfulness with the English language that is grounded in contemporary culture"

Research methodology. The neologisms appeared in two books of the series, including the names of spells, creatures and magical objects, were selected for the study. Each new word was analyzed from the point of view of morphology and semantics, lexical units and mechanisms of their formation, as well as cultural and symbolic meanings were identified. The method of contextual analysis was used to determine the function and meaning of neologism in specific plot situations.

One of the key features of neologisms in the Harry Potter series is their use of linguistic creativity, such as wordplay and phonological manipulation. For example, the word "Quidditch" is formed by combining the words "quaffle" and "snitch," which are two key elements of the game. As language scholar Mark Liberman notes, "the creation of new words through wordplay and phonological manipulation is a common feature of neologisms, and can contribute to their memorability and distinctiveness". Another key aspect of the semantic analysis of neologisms in the Harry Potter series will be the examination of semantic fields, which are groups of words that share similar meanings or associations. As language scholar John Sinclair notes, "semantic fields can reveal the cognitive and cultural aspects of language use, and can provide insights into the way in which people organize and understand the world around them".

One of the most commonly used word formation processes in the Harry Potter series is affixation, the process of adding a prefix or suffix to an existing word to create a new word. For example, the word "invisibility" is formed by adding the suffix "-ity" to the root word "invisible." According to linguistic scholar M.A.K. Halliday, affixation is a productive and common word formation process in English, and is used in a variety of contexts to create new words. Another word formation process used by J.K. Rowling in the Harry Potter series is compounding, the process of combining two or more words to create a new word. For example, the word "Hogwarts" is formed by combining the words "hog" and "warts." According to language scholar David Crystal, compounding is

a fundamental aspect of word formation in many languages, and is particularly important in English, which has a rich tradition of compound words.

Neologism neologisms formed with the help of borrowing. The first neologism to start with is called **Gryffindor**, who appeared in the first book of the series. Gryffindor is one of the four Houses of Hogwarts School that Rowling created in her Harry Potter series. This is derived from the Latin word '**Griffin**,' which refers to a legendary creature with the body of a lion. While '**dor**' is a French word that means '**gold**'. We'll get '**Griffin of Gold**' by merging them. Rowling thus borrowed and mixed both words to build a new lexical item representing the House of Gryffindor, which is represented by The lion and the golden hue.

The second lexical unit which belongs to this category is **Lumos**. This neologism refers to a famous spell in Harry Potter, which is also called the Wand-Lighting Charm. This latter allows wizards to cast light from the tip of their wands to lighten up the place. The word appeared in the second book. The spell **Lumos** is formed from the Latin term 'lumen,' which means light, and 'os,' which simply means to have something; so, combining the two gives us the expression 'to provide light,' which is exactly what the spell does.

Neologisms formed using derivation and compounding. The word **Muggle** is composed of two components: mug + -le. The first component is the word 'mug' which means according to the Oxford Dictionary: a person who is stupid and easy to trick. While the second one is the suffix -le. Therefore, Rowling combined the two parts to come up with this neologism. One can say that there is a clear relation between the definition of the English word 'mug' and the invented one 'muggle'. That is, both of these words share the same characteristic of foolishness. Seeker is the second neologism in the category of derivation. This later is one of a collection of words devised by the author to establish a comprehensive lexicology for a magical sport known as Quidditch. The term Seeker refers to a game character. That means, this player's primary goal is to catch a unique ball in the game.

The word Hufflepuff is formed from the compound '**huffle**' which means 'to blow in gusts' (Merriam Dictionary), whereas the second compound 'puff' means 'a short, explosive burst of breath or wind' (Oxford Dictionary). Also 'Huffing and puffing' suggests hard work (The Harry Potter Lexicon), which is related to the members who belong to this House, for that they are not very intelligent yet hard workers. The second invented word by Rowling is another name related to the four Houses which is Ravenclaw. This latter is the Hogwarts

house of founder Rowena Ravenclaw. **Mudblood** is another neologism created through the compounding process. This word is simply formed from combining both nouns: 'mud' which means wet earth that is soft and sticky, and 'blood' which is the red liquid that flows through the bodies of humans and animals (Oxford Dictionary).

Neologism formed using blending and coinage. The first invented word to begin with is called, **Animagus**. It means the ability to turn into a certain animal at any moment. The word Animagus is formed from the clipping two lexical units and then combining together. In other words, the English word 'animal' is clipped into 'anim', and with the addition of the Latin word 'magus', which means 'magic user', Rowling, finally came with the word Animagus, which refers literally to a wizard with animal abilities.

Pensive is the second neologism that emerges from this word-formation process. The Pensieve is a magical item that is used to evaluate memories. It resembles a small stone or metal basin into which runes and weird symbols have been carved and precious stones have been set (The Harry Potter Wiki). This coined term is a mix of 'pensive' and 'sieve'. 'Pensive' is derived from French and originally from the Latin 'pensare,' which means 'to consider,' and in modern English usage indicates 'thoughtful' or 'reflective'. 'Sieve' refers to an object used to separate undesired stuff from wanted material. **Quidditch** is the first neologism to be introduced. This neologism refers to the only sport in Harry Potter's wizarding realm. is a fast, risky, and entertaining game in which two teams fight for points by hurling a ball - the Quaffle - through hoops on either end. This word invented by Rowling has no records among the other languages, hence, it is a coined word. Moreover, Rowling (1999) claimed that: "I invented Quidditch while spending the night in a very small room in the Bournville Hotel in Didsbury, Manchester" (AmazonUK).

Conclusion

The most commonly used processes in her way of creating new words, according to the findings, are Borrowing and Compounding, for that approximately half of the data was included in this category. Since Rowling was often acquainted with languages, especially old ones, she used this quality in her favour to come up with new words (such as the list of spells in the saga), thus, the Borrowing process was the

most one to be used. Moreover, the analysis showed that the Compounding process was also frequently used. Words like Ravenclaw, Mudblood, Hufflepuff, and Hippogriff all belong to the Compounding process, which as a result, reveal that the author used this process more often.

References:

1. Algeo, John 1991. Fifty Years among the New Words: A Dictionary of Neologisms. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
2. Arnold – Арнольд И. В. 1986. Лексикология Современного Английского Языка:
3. McArthur, F., & McArthur, T. (1992). The Oxford companion to the English language. Oxford: Oxford University Press
4. Rowling, J. K. (1998). Harry Potter and the philosophers stone: vol. 1. London: Bloomsbury.
5. Rowling, J. K. (1999). Harry Potter and the chamber of secrets. Thorndike, ME: Thorndike Press
6. Oxford Dictionaries. Available at <http://oxforddictionaries.com/>
7. Book analysis and glossary: <https://bookanalysis.com/harry-potter/glossary/>